

Breeding methods

✓ Development of dihaploid rice lines through anther culture (I)

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We developed homozygous rice lines through anther culture, using crosses of blast (Bl)-resistant (indica/japonica) Korean varieties with Bl-susceptible Egyptian varieties.

Anthers from five F_1 crosses were inoculated on callus induction media G1, Fj, and L8, used routinely in the IRRI Tissue Culture Laboratory. The media varied in their basal composition and in 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA), and kinetin (Kin) concentrations. Calli were plated in eight regeneration media differing in Kin, NAA, and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) concentrations.

Callus induction efficiency in all three media was relatively high, indicating that all could be used for these crosses (Table 1). Callus induction percentage varied with genotype; those with a japonica female parent were more responsive. For example, Giza 171/C731135 had the highest callus production percentage on G1 and L8.

Green plant regeneration ranged from 0.4% to 7.7% (Table 2). Genotypes

Table 1. Calli induced from F_1 crosses in different callus induction media.^a IRRI, 1990 dry season (DS).

Cross combination (F_1)	G1		Fj		L8		Av calli produced ^b (%)
	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	
Nabda/Milyang 85	660	27.3	660	39.3	1080	50.5	41.1
Giza 14/Milyang 85	2040	41.4	1320	37.1	1320	37.8	39.2
GZ1343-8/C731135	840	33.3	1020	30.8	900	43.3	35.6
Giza 171/C731135	1440	60.4	2220	30.3	1500	51.3	44.8
GZ3030-11-1-3/Suweon 346	600	19.1	720	18.7	720	11.1	16.1
Total	5580		5940		5520		
Average ^a (%)		41.4		40.6		41.4	

^aConcentrations of 2,4-D, NAA, and Kin (mg/liter) = G1 = 2.0, 2.5, 0.75, Fj = 0.5, 2.5, 0.5, L8 = 0.5, 3.5, 2.0.

^bAnthers producing callus / Total anthers plated $\times 100$

Table 2. Green plant regeneration from 5 F_1 crosses in 8 media. IRRI, 1990 DS.

Cross combination (F_1)	Regeneration frequency (%)								Calli producing green plants	
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	SK-11	no.	% ^a
Nabda/Milyang 85	4.2	5.9	6.0	1.7	5.6	8.4	9.5	8.7	61	6.2
Giza 14/Milyang 85	3.6	4.4	6.5	5.1	4.6	7.6	3.1	4.7	87	4.7
GZ1343-8/C731135	0	1.2	2.5	0.6	0.7	0	0	2.8	9	0.8
Giza 171/C731135	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.6	10	0.4
GZ3030-11-1-3/Suweon 346	8.9	2.9	2.2	6.7	2.0	1.5	1.8	5.7	23	7.7
Calli producing green plants (no.)	18	24	27	20	20	25	27	29	190	
Average ^a (%)	2.7	2.8	3.0	2.4	3.1	4.1	3.3	3.6	-	3.1

^aCalli (no.) producing green plants / Calli (total no.) transferred $\times 100$

differed in their response to different plant regeneration media. Media M6, M7, and SK-11 gave the highest green plant percentages. Kin concentrations of M6, M7, and SK-11 were 8, 16, and 1 mg/liter, respectively. BAP (1 mg/liter) and casein hydrolysate (500 mg/liter)

were added to the SK-11 medium.

This study produced 794 homozygous diploid plants from 190 calli derived from the anther culture of five F_1 crosses. These anther culture-derived lines will be tested against available Bl races under Egyptian conditions. □